

Substrate integrated waveguide dual-band ISM antenna for wireless sensors

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Abstract—A planar dual-band circular antenna for a chemical wireless sensor network is presented in this paper. Four antennas compose the wireless sensor package and one antenna is selected at a given time using an SP4T switch. This work describes the unit antenna used to transmit sensor information to a nearby hub that operates in the ISM bands. The antenna is composed of concentric shorted annular rings using substrate integrated waveguides and includes a circular patch at its center. The antenna presents two types of radiation patterns, one omnidirectional in the azimuth plane at 2.4 GHz, and one unidirectional in the elevation plane at 5.8 GHz. The simulated gains obtained at 2.4 GHz and 5.8 GHz are 2.98 dB and 7 dB, respectively.

Index Terms—ISM Band, SIW, omnidirectional antenna, directional antenna, wireless sensor, MIMO.

I. INTRODUCTION

A planar dual-band antenna with multiband has the reliability and simplicity required to be integrated into chemical sensors heads, operating at infrared wavelengths [1], and respective optoelectronics in a package. ISM-band antennas are usually employed to undertake high quality data transmission using unlicensed bands. In previous recent years, the substrate integrated waveguide (SIW) structure has been used for the production of high performance planar circuits [2]. SIW technology has a good and simple fabrication yield with planar form, resulting easy to integrate with other components, enabling RF circuits for high data transmission [3], [4]. Several passive and active RF circuits have been proposed using SIW technology, among these circuits, are resonators, couplers, and antennas [5], [6]. A loop-type antenna with dual-band omnidirectional patterns is presented in [7]. A compact design with two modes at a single resonance frequency with two input probe feeds for MIMO applications is shown in [8], this antenna is done in a complex multilayer structure and provides low gain. However, there are few ISM antennas with multiband and dual-mode characteristics simultaneously. In [2] a circular patch antenna with a bandwidth below 0.5 GHz for WiFi applications is proposed. The antenna structure is based on adding a set of conductive vias, this design has a gain of 6 dB with single-band operation. In order to deploy a wireless sensor network for remote monitoring of

chemical contamination, a dual-band antenna operating in the industrial, scientific and medical (ISM) frequency bands is designed, fabricated and measured. Section II describes the antenna design and parameters used in its implementation. The measurement and simulation results are presented in section III. Finally, section IV provides a conclusion for this work.

II. ISM ANTENNA FOR WIRELESS SENSORS

Fig. 1 shows the proposed antenna design. The design is based on previous work described in [10]. The antenna dimensions are presented in Table I. In this paper, an outer ring is added to the antenna with SIW via holes that allows obtaining a good impedance match and isolates port 1 from frequencies above 2.4 GHz. The outer antenna has two radius R_1 and R_2 , with a slot width w_1 . The inner antenna has a radius corresponding to R_3 in Fig.1, and resonates at 5.8 GHz. A Taconic $RF - 30$ substrate is used to design the antenna, with a thickness $t = 1.52$ mm and a dielectric constant of 2.78. Fig. 2 shows the simulated comparison between the design in [10], labeled without SIW outer ring and the antenna described in this paper, which includes the SIW outer ring. It is apparent from Fig. 2 that the outer SIW ring added in this work improves potential interference mitigation from resonant frequencies over 2.4 GHz. Design theory for this antenna can be obtained in [10]– [13]. Table II shows the simulated comparison between the original design in [10] and this work using the same substrate, for the 2.4 GHz band. A slight increase in bandwidth and gain can be obtained by adding the SIW outer ring to the design in [10]. In this paper, a single layer structure, two probe-fed, dual-band circular antenna using SIW cavities is described. One circular patch at the center of the antenna operates at 5.8 GHz. A short circuited annular ring slot antenna operates at 2.4GHz. The resonant frequencies of different modes can be calculated using (1) [14].

$$f_{mn} = \frac{K_{mn}C}{2\pi R_{ave}\sqrt{\epsilon_r}} \quad (1)$$

Where the indexes mn is the order of modes, ϵ_r is the dielectric value and c is the velocity of the light in vacuum. K_{mn} is the eigenvalue obtained according to the boundary condition. The resonance wavelength of the TM mode is approximately equal to the average circumferential length of the ring resonant. However, it's equal to $2\pi R_{ave}$. Where $R_{ave} = (R_1 + R_2)/2$, R_1 , R_2 can show the outer and inner radius of the circular ring antenna.

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Fig. 1. Proposed antenna geometry (a) Top view without SIW cavity[10] ; (b) Top view with SIW cavity (proposed antenna) (c) side view.

In addition to the simple cavity model, the structure can be considered as a SIW cavity bounded by electric walls between the inner and outer radius [11]. According to theory, the electrical field has a z direction component, with an arbitrary position point (ρ, ϕ, z) in the SIW annular cavity, as shown in Fig.1. The electric field in cylindrical coordinates can be estimated using the empirical equation in (2)[10].

$$E_z = E_0 \cos n\phi [A_n J_n(K_r \rho) + B_n Y_n(K_r \rho)] \quad (2)$$

TABLE I
ANTENNA DESIGN PARAMETERS IN MILLIMETERS

Parameter	R_{siw}	$R1$	$R2$	$R3$
Value	39.42	32.12	16.1	8.2
P1	P2	t	d	$W1$
25.5	2.9	1.52	1	3

III. ISM ANTENNA RESULTS

The proposed antenna is simulated using HFSS and CST commercial software, CST software is based on the integral

method and HFSS is based on the finite element method (FEM). The two circular antennas in Fig.1 are well isolated using the SIW metalized vias. The TM₁₀ mode current distribution at 2.4 GHz is concentrated around the outer antenna (see Fig.3a) and produces a quasi-omnidirectional pattern. The TM₁₁ mode current distribution at the inner patch antenna (see Fig.3b) produces perpendicular radiation with respect to the planar antenna state.

Fig. 2. Comparison between the work in [10] (without SIW outer ring) and the antenna described in this work with the added SIW outer ring. .

Fig.2 show the comparison between the two simulations of reflection coefficient, with and without SIW cavity. Another hand, this results show the important parameter $w1$, when to decrease $w1$, we have a good results and can delete the other resonance frequencies.

Fig. 3. Current density (a) TM₀₁ mode at 2.4 GHz, (b) TM₁₁ mode at 5.8 GHz.

The antenna prototype is fabricated and measured after optimization performed through simulations. A photograph of the antenna top side is shown in Fig.4a, and Fig.4b shows the antenna bottom side.

The simulated and measured reflection coefficient results are shown in Fig.5. The simulated and measured results are in good agreement, except for a slight frequency shift of the TM₁₁ mode, which may be caused by the probe-feed position displacement after fabrication and by fabrication tolerances. The measured relative bandwidth for this antenna is around 89 MHz at 2.4 GHz and 220 MHz at 5.8 GHz, corresponding to 2.2 % and 5.7 % bandwidths at 2.4GHz and 5.8 GHz, respectively. A high isolation between the feeding probes

Fig. 4. Photograph of the antenna prototype, (a) antenna top side, (b) antenna bottom side.

is obtained by dividing the antennas using the SIW vias, measurement and simulation results related to the isolation between ports is shown in Fig.6. The isolation (transmission coefficient between ports 1 and 2), is below -26 dB, thus the two antennas operate independently.

Fig. 5. Simulation and measured reflection coefficient of the antenna, (a) S11 for 2.4 GHz operation (b) S22 for 5.8 GHz operation.

The simulated antenna gains are about 3 dB and 7 dB at 2.4 GHz and 5.8 GHz, respectively. Antenna radiation patterns were measured in an anechoic chamber for the two antenna bands of operation. Fig. 7 shows the radiation patterns

corresponding to the 2.4 GHz band and Fig. 8 shows the radiation patterns corresponding to the 5.8 GHz band. A good agreement between measurement and simulation is obtained regarding the radiation pattern results for the two antenna bands of operation, as shown in Figs. 7 and 8.

Fig. 6. Simulated and measured isolation between port1 and port2.

Fig. 7. Simulated and measured gains of the antenna.

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE OF THE PROPOSED ANTENNA AS COMPARED TO OTHER PUBLISHED ANTENNA [NOTICE: OMNIDIRECTIONAL=O-D AND UNIDIRECTIONAL=U-D]

$f_1=2.4\text{GHz}$ $f_2=5.8\text{GHz}$	Gain [dB]		Bandwidth[MHz]		direction	
	f_1	f_2	f_1	f_2	f_1	f_2
[10]	1.73	5.4	48.7	200	O-D	U-D
[15]	2.07	1.17	250	250	U-D	O-D
[16]	2.02	4.06	200	650	O-D	O-D
[17]	2.01	3.45	350	1000	O-D	O-D
proposed antenna	2.98	7	56.3	230	O-D	U-D

IV. CONCLUSION

The paper proposed a dual-band two-port SIW cavity antenna. The antenna is composed of two independent antennas operating with different modes and effectively isolated using

Fig. 8. Normalized simulated and measured radiation pattern of the antenna (a) E-field at 2.4GHz; (b) H-field at 2.4GHz.

Fig. 9. Normalized simulated and measured radiation pattern of the antenna (a) E-field at 2.4GHz; (b) H-field at 5.8GHz.

SIW metalized vias. The antenna resonant frequencies can be tuned independently for ISM dual-band operation. The planar antenna structure and its performance make it a suitable candidate for integration with chemical sensor heads for wireless sensor networks.

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